

THE EFFECT OF ARCHITECTURE ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF KNITTED COMPOSITES

K.O. Anwar¹, P.J. Callus¹, K.H. Leong², J. I. Curiskis³ & I. Herszberg¹

¹ *Sir Lawrence Wackett Centre for Aerospace Design and Technology, Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology, GPO Box 2476V, Melbourne, VIC 3001, Australia.*

² *Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures Ltd., 506 Lorimer Street, Fishermens Bend, VIC 3207, Australia.*

³ *Department of Textile Technology, University of New South Wales, Sydney, NSW 2052, Australia.*

SUMMARY: The aim of this paper is to investigate the tensile and compression properties, and failure mechanisms, of three different Milano ribs and one 1x1 rib weft-knit architecture. These fabrics were impregnated with vinyl ester resin to make thin, flat panels using the resin transfer moulding technique. The fibre volume fractions of the composites were maintained constant at approximately 53%. Tensile and compression specimens were cut in both the wale and the course directions and then tested to failure. Fractography was performed using a stereo optical microscope to establish the locus of failure. The wale-tested specimens were superior in tensile properties to the course-tested specimens. Tensile properties were greatly affected by the loop structure of the knitted fabrics, whereas compression properties were almost independent of test direction, loop length and loop density. It was observed that tensile fracture occurred in the planes of lowest fibre content for both specimens tested in the wale as well as in the course directions. This coincided with fibre fractures at legs of the loops for the wale-tested specimens and at needle-sinker loops for the course-tested specimens.

KEYWORDS: knit, rib, milano, wale, course, loop length, loop density, anisotropy.

INTRODUCTION

Considerable research has been directed at understanding the behaviour of composites made using textile manufacturing techniques in an attempt to gain industrial acceptance. One of these textile techniques, knitting, has been used, to produce structural preforms that provide the required fibre orientations and through-the-thickness fibre reinforcement. The near net shape manufacture of knitted preforms and their excellent drapability hold promise to be used in the composite manufacturing industry as cost effective and mechanically efficient structural components. Unfortunately, there is insufficient understanding of the effect of knitted textile reinforcements on the mechanical behaviour of structural composites.

Marvin [1] is believed to be the earliest worker to have studied the tensile properties of knitted glass/phenolic laminates with a view to replacing the metallic nose cones of subsonic and supersonic missiles. Rudd *et al.* [2] investigated plain weft-knit glass/polyester laminates both experimentally and analytically. Attempts were made to improve the stiffness of the laminates by using cross-floated knitted fabric. Verpoest and Dendauw [3] showed

experimentally that plain weft knit glass/epoxy laminates were anisotropic and dependent upon the knit architecture, fibre volume fraction and degree of fabric stretching. Fatigue properties of weft knitted composites were investigated by Chou *et al.* [4]. Wu *et al.* [5] showed that knitted structures greatly affect the in-plane anisotropic nature, tensile strength, and modulus of basic warp-knit fabric-reinforced composites. Ramakrishna and Hull [6] studied experimentally the tensile properties of 1x1 rib weft-knit carbon-fibre-fabric/epoxy laminates with and without inlay fibres. Significant increases in the modulus and tensile strength were achieved by inserting unidirectional tows of carbon fibres in the course direction. More recently, Herszberg and colleagues [7-10] studied experimentally the mechanical performance of weft-knit E glass/epoxy composites using the Milano rib and half-Milano architecture. The tensile properties of the half-Milano were found to be inferior to those of the Milano rib and extremely anisotropic.

For this study, an epoxy-based vinyl ester resin was used. Derakane 411C-50 resin was chosen because it has an exceptionally low resin viscosity and has been specially designed for the resin transfer moulding (RTM) process. Four different weft knit structures were studied. The effects of knit architecture, fibre orientation, loop lengths and loop density (course/cm and wale/cm) on the tensile and compression properties were discussed. Failure mechanisms were examined based on fractographic studies using a stereo optical microscope.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Three different Milano rib (M1, M3, M9) and one 1x1 rib (R3) weft-knit architectures were produced from E-glass yarns by combining 2x68 tex on an 8-gauge V-bed knitting machine. Components of weft-knit loop structure are shown in Fig. 1. Rib knit fabrics contain loops in alternate groups of wales meshed on one side of the fabric with the loops in the remaining wales meshed on the opposite side. Each wale contains either all plain stitches or all purl or back stitches. In the 1x1 rib structure, every second stitch alternates from front to back. Fig. 2(a) shows a schematic presentation of 1x1 rib structure. In the Milano, shown in Fig. 2(b), each complete repeat of the structure consists of three courses - two rows of plain or back loops, knitted on two separate sets of needles, which are held together by a row of 1x1 rib course. Since the face and the back surface are identical in construction, the resultant fabric is completely balanced.

Thin flat composite panels (405 mm x 540 mm) were fabricated by the resin transfer moulding technique using Derakane 411C-50 vinyl ester resin. Resin injection was performed with 210 KPa at the inlet and 100 KPa vacuum at the outlet. The panels were postcured at 120°C for an hour to optimise resin properties. In order to maintain fairly constant specimen thickness of 3 mm and fibre volume fraction of approximately 53%, the number of layers of each preform were 6, 6, 6 and 10 in types R3, M3, M1, and M9 respectively. Panel details are summarised in Table 1.

Fig. 1: Components of weft-knitted loop structure

Fig. 2: Schematic diagrams of weft-knitted fabrics

(a) 1 x 1 rib structure

(b) Full Milano structure

Table 1: Variation of weft-knit architectures and panel details

Type	Loop density		Loop length		Panel details		
	Course density (C/cm)	Wale density (W/cm)	Plain course (mm)	Rib course (mm)	Fabric layers/test panel	Areal Weight (g/m ²)	Volume Fraction (%)
R3	10.2	3.92	-	6.2	6	675	52.94
M3	9.2	4.70	6.2	6.5	6	680	53.33
M1	8.8	4.50	5.8	6.6	6	664	52.10
M9	6.2	2.80	7.8	9.1	10	415	54.25

Tensile specimens (250 mm x 25 mm) were cut from the panels parallel to the wale (W) and the course (C) direction. Tensile tests were performed on an MTS machine using a 128 mm gauge length extensometer, at room temperature and at a test speed of 0.5 mm/min. 250 series strain gauges were bonded to the surface of the tensile specimens. Compression specimens (56 mm x 25 mm) were also cut in both the wale and the course direction and tested to failure using a modified IITRI (Illinois Institute of Technology Research Institute) test rig on an MTS machine at a speed of 0.5 mm/min. The ultimate strength, strain to failure, elastic modulus and Poisson’s ratio were determined for each specimen. Elastic modulus and Poisson’s ratio were calculated in the strain range of 0.1 to approximately 0.3%. Fracture paths were recorded by taking photomicrographs of the tested specimens.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile properties

As shown in Table 1, the loop length and loop density for the three Milano rib and 1x1 rib architectures were different. The results of tensile tests are summarised in Table 2. It was observed that the tensile strength, tensile modulus and strain to failure in the wale direction were higher than those in the course direction.

Table 2: Tensile properties of weft knitted fabric-reinforced composites

Type	Strength (MPa)		Strength Ratio	Tensile Modulus (GPa)		Strain to Failure (%)	
	W	C	W/C	W	C	W	C
R3	96.0	75.8	1.27	14.7	14.0	1.40	0.84
M3	122	82.8	1.47	14.9	13.2	2.20	1.40
M1	134	83.0	1.62	14.3	12.3	2.40	1.40
M9	160	113	1.41	15.5	14.1	2.40	2.00

Figure 3 shows the typical tensile stress-strain curves for all four weft-knit composite laminates. On the whole, the response of all laminates was linear up to a ‘knee point’, which occurred at a strain of approximately 0.3%. Strains at that point were almost independent of the testing direction for all four structures. From the ‘knee point’, all specimens displayed significant softening, which continued until failure.

Fig. 3: Tensile stress-strain curves of weft-knit composites.

Fig. 4: Tensile properties of weft knitted composites (a) strength, (b) elastic Modulus, (c) strain to failure, and (d) Poisson's ratio

Inspection of Fig. 4(a) revealed that the tensile strength in the wale direction was much higher than that in the course direction for all laminates. It was also observed that the tensile strength

in the wale direction increased with increasing loop length and decreasing loop density. This effect was found to be less significant in the course direction.

Figure 4(b) shows that the tensile modulus was slightly higher in the wale direction than in the course direction for each laminate type. For either test direction, modulus was almost constant, despite changes in loop length and loop density.

As shown in Fig. 4(c), the tensile strain to failure in the wale direction was also observed to be higher than that in the course direction. As loop length increased or loop density decreased, tensile strains increased in both testing directions.

The Poisson's ratio shown in Fig. 4(d) slightly increased in the wale direction as loop length increased and loop density decreased, whereas it was almost independent of loop structure in the course direction.

Figure 5 shows photomicrographs of tensile tested specimens. Fracture appeared to have occurred in the planes of lowest fibre content for both specimens tested in the wale as well as in the course directions. This coincided with fibre fractures at legs of the loops for the wale-tested specimens and at needle-sinker loops for the course-tested specimens.

Fig.5: Micrographs of fracture surface of weft-knit composites tested in the a) wale and (b) course direction

Fibre bundle debonding and resin cracking from the debonded sites were evidenced in Fig. 5. The microcracks generated from the debonded sites propagated through the adjacent resin-rich areas within the knit structure. In the wale direction, the fibre bundles were oriented at a denser proportion compared with the course direction. This was caused by the course density along the wale direction being about 50% higher than the wale density along the course direction. Hence the wale-tested specimens were capable of absorbing significantly more energy before failure compared to the course-tested specimens. Such phenomena are in agreement with the observations reported by Ramakrishna and Hull [6].

Again, it was observed that tensile properties for the knit structure, M9 were higher than the others in both testing directions. It was assumed that the defects in the weft-knit structure which caused the fibre to fail, were the highly curved or looped interlocking regions. Table 1 showed that, type M9 displayed the largest loop length and smallest loop density and thus it contained the least number of such defects in both directions when compared to the others.

Therefore, type M9 proved to be the strongest among all the knit structures considered in this study.

Compression Properties

Figure 6 shows the response of the weft-knit composite structures under compression. The curves were almost overlapping regardless of the test direction and the knee point occurred at a higher strain level of about 1.0%. Compression properties are summarised in Table 3.

Fig. 6: Compression stress-strain curves of weft-knit composites

Table 3: Compression properties of weft knitted fabric-reinforced composites

Type	Strength (MPa)		Strength ratio W/C	Compressive Modulus (MPa)		Strain to Failure (%)	
	W	C		W	C	W	C
R3	162	159	1.02	10.5	9.82	2.10	2.50
M3	169	163	1.04	11.9	9.65	2.00	2.50
M1	160	156	1.03	10.0	11.4	1.80	1.70
M9	180	181	0.99	12.0	11.3	1.90	2.20

Compression strengths, moduli and failure strains are shown in Fig. 7. Compression properties of weft-knit composite structures appeared to be almost independent of the knitting direction and loop structure. It is proposed that under compression, knitted composites act as short fibre reinforced composites, where the loop length is analogous to the short fibre length. The elastic-plastic analysis of short fibre composites by Agarwal and Broutman [11] suggests that, for the same applied load on the composite the stress within fibres will remain approximately constant when the short fibre aspect ratio, l/d exceeds 25 (where l =fibre length and d =fibre diameter). In the present study of weft-knit structures under compression, the ratio l/d ranges from 480 to 700. Since $l/d \gg 25$, the stress supported by these fibres is dependent only on applied stress to composite, not on loop length. Hence knitted structures with different loop lengths showed no significant variation in their compression properties.

Fig. 7: Compression properties of weft-knit composites (a) strength, (b) elastic modulus, and (c) strain to failure

CONCLUSIONS

The weft-knit composite laminates tested were anisotropic in tensile strength and strain to failure, but the elastic tensile modulus of these composites were similar in both the wale and the course direction. In the wale direction, the fibre bundles were oriented at a denser proportion compared with the course direction. Hence the tensile properties in the wale direction were superior to the course direction.

Tensile strength and strain to failure were greatly affected by the loop length and loop density. With increasing loop length, the tensile strength and strain to failure increased, whereas loop density showed an inverse effect on these properties. The change was more predominant in the wale direction than in the course direction. On the whole, the Milano rib structure seemed to be stronger than 1x1 rib structure.

The tensile Poisson's ratio slightly increased in the wale direction with increasing loop length and decreasing loop density, whereas it was almost independent of loop structure in the course direction.

Despite the influence of test direction, loop length and loop density on tensile properties, the compression properties were seen to be almost unaffected by these parameters.

It was observed that tensile fracture occurred in the planes of lowest fibre content for both specimens tested in the wale as well as in the course directions. This coincided with fibre fractures at legs of the loops for the wale-tested specimens and at needle-sinker loops for the course-tested specimens.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to S. Savçi and T. Sifniotis of the Department of Textile Technology, University of New South Wales for useful discussions and the supply of knitted fabrics and the data outlined in Table 1. Thanks are also due to K. Houghton of CRC-ACS for assistance in test panel manufacture and specimen preparation, and to M. Wilson of Department of Aerospace Engineering, RMIT for assistance in conducting mechanical tests.

REFERENCES

1. Marvin, A. G., "The Development of Knitted Glass Fabrics for Use in Resin Lamination", *M.Sc. Thesis*, University of Strathclyde, 1969.
2. Rudd, C.D, Owen, M. J. & Middleton, V., "Mechanical Properties of Weft Knit Glass Fibre/Polyester Laminates", *Journal of Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 39, 1990, pp. 261-277.
3. Verpoest, I. and Dendauw, J., "Mechanical Properties of Knitted Glass Fibre/Epoxy Resin Laminates", (*Proc. Conf.*) *37th International SAMPE Symposium*, March 9-12, 1992, pp. 369-377.
4. Chou, S., Chen, H.C. and Lai, C.C., "The Fatigue Properties of Weft-Knit Fabric Reinforced Epoxy Resin Composites", *Journal of Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 45, 1992, pp. 283-291.
5. Wu, W.L., Kotaki, M. and Fujita, A., "Mechanical Properties of Warp- Knitted, Fabric-Reinforced Composites", *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 12, No. 10, 1993, pp. 1096-1110.
6. Ramakrishna, S. and Hull, D., "Tensile Behaviour of Knitted Carbon-Fibre-Fabric/Epoxy Laminates-- Part I: Experimental", *Journal of Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 50, No. 2, 1994, pp. 237-247.
7. Bannister, M.K and Herszberg, I., "The Manufacture and Analysis of Composite Structures from Knitted Preforms", (*Proc. Conf.*) *Fourth International Conference on Automated Composites*, September 6-7, 1995, Nottingham, U.K., Vol. 2, pp. 397-404.

8. Herszberg, I., Falzon, P.J., Leong, K.H. and Bannister, M.K., "Bearing Strength of Glass/Epoxy Composites Manufactured from Weft-Knitted E-glass Fabric", (*Proc. Conf. The First Australian Congress on Applied Mechanics*, February 21-23, 1996, Melbourne, Australia, pp. 279-284.
9. Leong, K.H., Falzon, P.J., Bannister, M.K. and Herszberg, I., "An Investigation of the Mechanical Performance of Weft-Knitted Milano Rib Glass/Epoxy Composites", Submitted to *Journal of Composites Science and Technology*, 1996.
10. Leong, K.H., Nyugen, M. and Herszberg, I., "The Effect of Deformation of Glass Fibre Knitted Fabrics on the Resultant Composite Tensile Properties", To be presented at *The Eleventh International Conference on Composite Materials, ICCM-11*, Gold coast, Australia, July 14-18, 1997.
11. Agarwal, B.D. and Broutman, L.J., "*Analysis and Performance of Fibre Composites*", Second Edition, Chapter 4, Pages 122-128.